

Oil Palm Loose Fruit Data Collector

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Abstract: *The conventional method to identify the detachment of oil palm loose fruit in indicating the harvesting readiness may delay loose fruit collection, resulting in lower oil extraction rates (OER) and reduced yield productivity. The loose fruit data collector tool has been innovative in detecting and collecting data on the detachment of loose fruit. The tool is equipped with a sensor mechanism that is powered up by the solar panel to detect the falling of loose fruit to the ground, detached from the fresh fruit bunch. Real-time data is captured and stored in the Blynk apps installed on mobile phones or computers, offering users flexible access. The tool provides real-time data on the harvest readiness index which enables the plantation to determine the optimal harvesting time thus reducing the time and reliance for workers to detect and identify loose fruit detachment. This tool, may improve the working efficiency of workers and enhance the harvesting time accuracy, maintaining high palm oil yield production and reducing waste in the production process, thus fostering SDG 8 and 12 goals.*

Keywords: oil palm loose fruit; detachment; sensor identification; real-time data; harvesting.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The detachment of oil palm loose fruit from ripen fresh fruit bunches (FFB) is an indicator for the readiness of that particular bunches to be harvested. The detection and collection of loose fruit is one of the crucial process in the harvesting activities that required major attention due to its economic value for upstream production of palm oil. Fruits from the outer diameter of a bunch contributes to 40 – 50% of palm oil (Gan et al., 1993; Henson, 2012). Moreover, the oil extraction rate (OER) may reduce by 0.92%, 0.46% and 0.37% for palm trees aged 1-5 years, 6-15 years, and over 15 years, respectively for non-collected loose fruits (Gan et al., 1993). Hence, if the loose fruits is not collected promptly, there will be a significant losses on the OER, leading to reduction of overall productivity.

Most of the time, the harvest readiness is assessed manually where it require workers to manually check the palm tree and estimate the bunch's age. Conventional methods of identifying and collecting loose fruits are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and prone to inefficiency as it relies on the worker's skill and experience. Human workers may overlook loose fruits, particularly in large

plantations where manual monitoring is challenging. Furthermore, delays in loose fruits detection and collection may lead to reduction of quality, resulting in lower oil extraction rates. To address these challenges, a tool equipped with a sensor system capable in real-time detecting and collecting data on loose fruit detachments from the FFB is innovated. The tool aims to facilitate efficiency in harvesting process, ensuring that loose fruits are identified and collected promptly, thereby decreasing waste and enhancing overall yield.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The Loose Fruit Data Collector is equipped with a sensor that build on a PVC pole and a transparent box is used to cover the sensor from rough weather. On the adjacent side where the sensor is installed, an opening is made on the PVC pole to provide a convenient access for the maintenance of the sensor. Then, a solar panel is provided and function as the power supply for the sensor.

Figure 1. Flowchart of project implementation.

3. FINDINGS

The Loose Fruit Data Collector is used to detect and collect oil palm loose fruit data. The tool would be placed near the oil palm tree in which it would be placed within 1 ft from the tip of the oil palm frond. A solar energy generated through the solar panel is used as the power supply for the sensor. The mechanism workflow of the Loose Fruit Data Collector shown on Figure 3; (a) the sensor would detect the falling of oil palm loose fruit to the ground, detached from the fresh fruit bunch (FFB), (b) the sensor would capture the data, (c) data captured submitted to Blynk Apps installed on mobile phone, computer or laptop, (d) data stored in the Blynk database. The tool provides a real-time data for the oil palm loose fruit enabling data access and store by users at anytime and anywhere, giving them flexibility and a timely decision-making.

Figure 2. Sketch of the Loose Fruit Data Collector.

Figure 3. Mechanism of the Loose Fruit Data Collector.

Figure 4. Loose Fruit Data Collector prototype.

4. DISCUSSION

The innovated tool able to provide a real-time data on the harvest readiness based on the detachment of loose fruit to the ground that indicate the ripeness of the oil palm fresh fruit bunches. Plantation managers and workers can accurately determine the optimal time to harvest the palm tree based on the data of the shedding loose fruit. Therefore, reduce the time and labor required for detection and counting of loose fruits, allowing for efficient harvesting activity. The patterns of the loose fruit shedding data also provide information on the oil palm tree health and productivity. This aids to a decision-making to plantation managers in pruning schedules, fertilization programs, disease management and other agricultural practices to optimize growth and fruiting cycles of the palm tree. The collected data also serve as an early estimate of the potential yield of palm oil and can be used to analyze the long-term trends of the plantation productivity.

The Loose Fruit Data Collector promotes energy sustainability as it relies on solar energy to operates and requires minimal workers intervention. The Loose Fruit Data Collector foster the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The use of this tool may improve the working efficiency of workers and reduce the physical burden, fostering SDG 8 through the oil palm industry. Moreover, the innovation of this tool is aligned with SDG 12 in which the tool enhances the harvesting time accuracy, maintaining high palm oil yield and reduce waste in the production process.

5. CONCLUSION

The Loose Fruit Data Collector facilitates the efficiency of harvesting activity in oil palm addressing the detachment of oil palm loose fruits that indicate the harvesting readiness of the loose fruit. This innovation product may help in the harvesting operation as well as other management practices of oil palm, thus, improving overall productivity of palm oil.

References

- Gan, L. T., Ho, C. Y., Chiew, J. S., & Lam, K. S. (1993). Optimum harvesting standards to maximize labour productivity and oil recovery. *1993 PORIM International Palm Oil Congress – Update and Vision(Agriculture)*. PORIM, Bangi. p. 195-211.
- Henson, I. E. (2012). Ripening, harvesting, and transport of oil palm bunches. *Palm Oil*, 137 -162.